

D8.1.2 Data Management Plan revision period I

Project ref. no.	H2020-MG-2018-SingleStage-INEA N° 824326
Project title	Revealing fair and actionable knowledge from data to support women's inclusion in transport systems,
Project duration	1 st November 2018 – 31 st October 2021 (36 months)
Website	www.diamond-project.eu
Related WP/Task	WP8 / T8.1
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document due date	30/04/2020 (M18)
Actual delivery date	30/04/2020 (M18)
Deliverable leader	Systematica Srl (SYS)
Document status	Submitted

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824326

Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	19/03/2020	Andrea Gorrini (SYS)	Draft version circulated to partners
0.2	23/03/2020	Yvonne Hail (STIR)	Draft version reviewed by Yvonne Hail
0.3	30/03/2020	Carol Bruce (TU Dublin)	Draft version reviewed by Carol Bruce
0.4	14/04/2020	Elena García (AITEC)	Draft version reviewed by Elena García
0.5	15/04/2020	Begoña Mateo (IBV)	Draft version reviewed by Begoña Mateo (IBV)
0.6	15/04/2020	Sara Poveda Reyes (AITEC)	Draft version reviewed by Sara Poveda Reyes
0.7	15/04/2020	Maria Chiara Leva (TU Dublin)	Draft version reviewed by Maria Chiara Leva (TU Dublin)
0.8	22/04/2020	Francisco Santarremigia (AITEC)	Draft version reviewed by Francisco Santarremigia (AITEC)
0.9	23/04/2020	Marthe Ozbolt (VELIB)	Draft version reviewed by Marthe Ozbolt (VELIB)
1.0	29/04/2020	Anahita Rezaallah (SYS)	Draft version reviewed by Anahita Rezaallah (SYS)
1.1	29/04/2020	Andrea Gorrini (SYS)	Draft version reviewed by Andrea Gorrini (SYS)
1.2	30/04/2020	Systematica S.r.l. (SYS)	Final complete version and validation.
1.3	30/04/2020	Project Coordinator	Final version submitted

Executive Summary

This document is the 'Deliverable 8.1.2: Data Management Plan revision period I' of the DIAMOND Project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement Number 824326.

The main aim of DIAMOND Project is to turn data into actionable knowledge with notions of fairness, in order to progress towards an inclusive and efficient transport system, by the development of a methodology based on the collection and analysis of disaggregated data, including new sources, analytics and management techniques.

This document is the second version of the Data Management Plan (DMP), consisting of detailed information regarding the type and format of data that have been collected and generated, its origin, data utility and how DIAMOND project research data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (i.e. FAIR).

The purpose of DMP is to provide the members of the consortium with an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy regarding all the datasets generated by the project. The DMP is a living document that will evolve during the lifespan of the project, the second version D8.1.3_Data Management Plan will be published by the end of project on November 30, 2021.

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Terminology and Acronyms

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
AITEC	Aitec Asesores Internacionales srl
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
CFCs	Cluster of Fairness Characteristics
D	Deliverable
DAD	Dynamic Argumentative Delphi
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
ENU	Edinburgh Napier University
EU	European Union
EURECAT	Eurecat - Centro Tecnológico de Cataluña
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FCs	Fairness Characteristics
FGC	Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya
FTTE	University of Belgrade
G&V	GENRE ET VILLE
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
H2020	Horizon 2020
IBV	Instituto de Biomecánica de Valencia
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
SYS	Systematica S.r.l.
TU Dublin	Technological University Dublin
UESI	Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index questionnaires
VELIB	Syndicat Mixte Autolib et Velib Métropole
WAVE	WAVE WOMEN AND VEHICLES IN EUROPE
WP	Work Package
ZTM	Miasto Stołeczne Warszawa

I. Introduction

The following document is the ‘Deliverable 8.1.2 Data Management Plan revision period I’ of the DIAMOND Project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement Number 824326. The main purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide the members of the consortium with an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy to be used with regard to the DIAMOND project research data.

The DMP is produced using the European Commission (EC) guideline of "Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan template" (2016). It covers the entire research data life cycle as it is shown in the Diamond project Deliverable 2.2 that illustrates the different phases of research data management and their relation.

This is based on the interdisciplinary methodology of the DIAMOND project¹ (see Section 1.1 and Figure 1), based on the collection and analysis of disaggregated data, including new sources, analytics and management techniques.

The DMP provides information regarding the purpose of data collection, the type and format of data collection, methods of re-using existing data, origin of data, expected size of data, data utility, how DIAMOND project research data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), data security and ethical issues.

As this document is the second version of the DMP², it provides an overview of data collection currently and describes the practical data management procedures implemented by the DIAMOND project. The DMP will be updated in Month 36 (D8.1.3).

1.1 Methodology for data collection

The main objective of DIAMOND project is to turn data into reliable and actionable knowledge for supporting the inclusion of women in transport systems as both users and employees. The document is focused on **four Use Cases**³:

- Use Case I: Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways);
- Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car;
- Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet;
- Use Case IV: Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols.

Within the objectives of the ‘Work Package 2 – Conceptual Framework’ and ‘Work Package 3 – Data collection’, data collection campaigns were executed on the basis of: the Inclusion Diamond representation⁴, the concept of the Polyhedral individual⁵, the Concept of Fairness⁶ and the unique

¹ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’.

² See ‘Deliverable 8.1.1 Data Management Plan’.

³ See ‘Deliverable D2.1 Use case definition’.

⁴ See ‘Deliverable D2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

⁵ See ‘Deliverable D2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

⁶ See ‘Deliverable D2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

methodological approach⁷ of the DIAMOND Project (see Diamond Deliverable 2.2). This was aimed at collecting **heterogeneous and disaggregated data** about people's needs in the transport sector, which are divided into two main categories:

- **Service and Employers' Provision Data:**
 - Structured data regarding the operation of transport services (Use Cases I and III) and job holders of the sector (Use Case IV);
 - Observations regarding relevant features of transportation settings (Use Cases I and III) and emotional responses to autonomous vehicles (Use Case II);
 - Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III) and job conditions and employability (Use Case IV);
 - Social media data from Twitter regarding geospatial/time-based information and the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III).
- **Users and Employees' Perception Data:**
 - DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires regarding the Fairness Characteristics (Use Cases I, II, III and IV).

As a preliminary step towards data collection, the methodological approach of the DIAMOND Project was based on the identification of a series of Fairness Characteristics (FCs) related to the inclusion of all users in the transport sector. FCs were defined and then validated through **Thematic Analysis**⁸, which was based on a review of the most relevant scientific literature and on the execution of a series of focus groups for each Use Case.

Within the objectives of 'Work Package 4 – Interdisciplinary model creation', the Service and Employers' Provision Database is planned to be analysed using factor and regression analysis and **Bayesian Network**, while the Users and Employees Perception Database will be analysed using **Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)**.

⁷ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁸ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

Figure 1 Data Life Cycle⁹.

Figure 2 Methodological approach to obtain fairness measures for each use case¹⁰.

⁹ See Hüser, F.J., Martinez, I.P., Elbæk, M.K., Fjeldhagen, M. (2016): Data Management Plan. Journal contribution.

¹⁰ See 'Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework'.

2. Data summary

2.1 What is the purpose of the data collection and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The purpose of data collection campaigns initiated by the DIAMOND project was to collect quantitative and qualitative data regarding the participation of users - in the transport sector both as users and jobholders. The data collection campaigns complied with all EU, national and institutional ethics and legal frameworks.

The data collected will be used to meet the main objective of the project mentioned in "Grant Agreement, Number 824326 – DIAMOND" and listed below: *"To turn data into actionable knowledge with notions of fairness, in order to progress towards an inclusive and efficient transport system"*, as well as following specific objectives listed below:

- Develop a conceptual framework for effective data collection to advance the understanding on user's needs, motivations and expectations on upcoming business and operational transport models and technologies;
- Identify and actively tackle gaps and opportunities for future inclusive transport systems;
- Build new comprehensive sets of disaggregated data with demographic and behavioural variables in mobility and transport scalable to population specificities;
- Carry out interdisciplinary data analysis to identify present and future behaviour patterns, gaps and opportunities for inclusive transport systems, including definitions of fairness;
- Turn knowledge into actionable tools by delivering new personalized tools for self-diagnose, decision support systems and modelling tools for inclusive measures;
- Validate the different tools included in different Use Cases (efficiency, effectiveness, impact, scalability, acceptance, replicability in different transport modes, etc.);
- Prove the value of integrating new data sets into transport operations for an inclusive and sustainable transport management, by measuring its impact on transport organizations;
- Replicate and generate new business opportunities, by showing examples of successful cases implemented in the project that could be translated into other modes of transport;
- Address all users' needs as users and jobholder considering them as Polyhedral Individuals with multiple characteristics: age, ethnic origin, social level, education, family composition, sexual identity and orientation, etc.; (intersectional approach)
- Generate and disseminate recommendations and protocols for a fair transport with the aim of engaging the transport community, public authorities and society at large;
- Develop a novel methodological approach and new datasets to implement new educational resources and strategies for fairness management;
- Developments and challenges related to inclusive mobility and related needs for skills and opportunities for professional careers will be reflected;
- Enabling participatory processes in knowledge building where participants provide their input, enabling an open, anonymous and wide co-creation process.

2.2 What types and formats of data were collected?

2.2.1 Type of data

The DIAMOND project collected and produced a wide range of both quantitative and qualitative data for four different Use Cases. This document includes information regarding the identification of dataset sources, data collection tools, data collection timeline and identifies the partner responsible for each data collection activity, which are summarized below:

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Leading Partner
Structured Data	To identify and characterise a short list of relevant metro and urban railway stations managed by FGC (Province of Barcelona, Spain) and ZTM (Warsaw Metropolitan Area, Poland), where to perform further data collection activities.	Open data (territorial, socio-demographic, mobility data, etc.) and proprietary data (travel ridership, etc.).	SYS.
Observations	To further characterize the selected metro and urban railway stations and to compare data with UESI questionnaires.	Assessment checklist: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	SYS.
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and to investigate their level of satisfaction with the characteristics of the selected stations.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, mobility patterns, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	TU Dublin.
Social Media Data	To characterize the selected stations through the opinion of the end-users by clustering Twitter data among space and time and by analysing hashtags and textual contents.	Twitter (disaggregated) data: geospatial data, time-based meta data, hashtags and textual contents.	EURECAT.
DAD survey questionnaires	To get the opinions of the end-users in order to weight/prioritize using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) the FCs (Level 2) identified through the Thematic Analysis for the Use Case I and clustered in a hierarchical model built by the clusters of fairness characteristics (CFCs) (Level 1) and FCs (Level 2).	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	AITEC.

Table 1 Description of Service and Employers' Provision Data and Users and Employees' Perception Data for the Use Case I

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Leading Partner
Observations	To identify stress triggers related to autonomous driving performance, focusing on gender.	Experiments in a driving simulator laboratory setting.	IBV.
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and to correlate their level of satisfaction with the autonomous driving performance experienced through the simulator.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, mobility patterns, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	TU Dublin.
Social Media Data	To analyse hashtags and textual contents.	Twitter (disaggregated) data: hashtags and textual contents.	EURECAT.
DAD survey questionnaires	Weight and prioritize the FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis and cluster in a hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs for the Use Case II.	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	AITEC.

Table 2 Description of Service and Employers' Provision Data and Users and Employees' Perception Data for the Use Case II.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Leading Partner
Structured Data	To identify a short list of relevant bike sharing pickup/return points managed by VELIB within the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France), where to perform future data collection activities.	Open data (territorial, socio-demographic, mobility data, travel demand data) and proprietary data (e.g. travel ridership).	SYS.
Observations	To further characterize the selected bike sharing pickup/return points and to compare data with UESI questionnaires.	Assessment checklist: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	SYS.
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and to correlate their level of satisfaction with the characteristics of the bike sharing pickup/return points.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, mobility patterns, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	TU Dublin.

Social Media Data	To characterize the selected pickup/return points through the opinion of the end-users by clustering Twitter data among space and time and by analysing hashtags and textual contents.	Twitter (disaggregated) data: geospatial data, time-based meta data, hashtag and text content.	EURECAT.
DAD survey questionnaires	To get the opinions of the end-users in order to weight/prioritize using AHP the FCs (Level 2) identified through the Thematic Analysis for the Use Case III and clustered in a hierarchical model built by the CFCs (Level 1) and FCs (Level 2)	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	AITEC.

Table 3 Description of Service and Employers' Provision Data and Users and Employees' Perception Data for the Use Case III.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Leading Partner
Structured Data	To define the level of participation of women to on-site and off-site professional jobs related to transport sector in several European Countries.	Open data and proprietary data.	TU Dublin.
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and career profiles of the employees and to correlate their level of satisfaction with the characteristics of the job conditions.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, career profiles, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	TU Dublin.
DAD survey questionnaires	To get the opinions of the end-users in order to weight/prioritize using AHP the FCs (Level 2) identified through the Thematic Analysis for the Use Case IV and clustered in a hierarchical model built by the CFCs (Level 1) and FCs (Level 2)	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	AITEC.

Table 4 Description of Service and Employers' Provision Data and Users and Employees' Perception Data for the Use Case IV.

2.2.2 Format of data

The collected data will be stored in several formats (e.g. documents, images, videos, data, numerical codes, maps and models). The following table provides an overview of file types for sharing, reuse and preservation:

Type of data	Acceptable formats for sharing, reuse and preservation	Other acceptable formats for data preservation
Tabular data with extensive metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SPSS portable format (.por) delimited text and command ('setup') file (SPSS, Stata, SAS, etc.) structured text or mark-up file of metadata information, e.g. DDI XML file 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> proprietary formats of statistical packages: SPSS (.sav), Stata (.dta), MS Access (.mdb/.accdb)
Tabular data with minimal metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> comma-separated values (.csv) tab-delimited file (.tab) delimited text with SQL data definition statements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> delimited text (.txt) with characters not present in data used as delimiters widely-used formats: MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), MS Access (.mdb/.accdb), dBase (.dbf), OpenDocument Spreadsheet (.ods)
Geospatial data vector and raster data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ESRI Shapefile (.shp, .shx, .dbf, .prj, .sbx, .sbn optional) geo-referenced TIFF (.tif, .tiff) CAD data (.dwg) tabular GIS attribute data Geography Markup Language (.gml) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ESRI Geodatabase format (.mdb) MapInfo Interchange Format (.mif) for vector data Keyhole Mark-up Language (.kml) Adobe Illustrator (.ai), CAD data (.dxf or .svg) binary formats of GIS and CAD packages
Textual data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rich Text Format (.rtf) plain text, ASCII (.txt) eXtensible Mark-up Language (.xml) text according to an appropriate Document Type Definition (DTD) or schema 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hypertext Mark-up Language (.html) widely-used formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx) some software-specific formats: NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti
Image data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TIFF 6.0 uncompressed (.tif) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg, .jp2) if originally created in this format GIF (.gif) TIFF other versions (.tif, .tiff) RAW image format (.raw) Photoshop files (.psd) BMP (.bmp) PNG (.png) Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF) (.pdf)

Audio data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Free Lossless Audio Codec (.flac) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MPEG-I Audio Layer 3 (.mp3) if originally created in this format Audio Interchange File Format (.aif) Waveform Audio Format (.wav)
Video data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MPEG-4 (.mp4) OGG video (.ogv, .ogg) motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVCHD video (.avchd)
Documentation and scripts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rich Text Format (.rtf) PDF/UA, PDF/A or PDF (.pdf) XHTML or HTML (.xhtml, .htm) OpenDocument Text (.odt) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> plain text (.txt) widely-used formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx), MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx) XML marked-up text (.xml) according to an appropriate DTD or schema, e.g. XHMTL 1.0

Table 5. File formats recommended for data sharing, reuse and preservation

2.3 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

The Structured Proprietary Data will be collected from consortium partner's user subscriptions such as VELIB, FGC, ZTM, G&V, WAVE etc. In addition, partners such as FGC and ZTM provided data regarding the design of the train stations (e.g. number of CCTV cameras) where available. The consortium takes into consideration the possibility to gather data from other sources such as ongoing or completed EU H2020 Projects (e.g. TInnGO project and MoTIV project).

2.4 What is the expected size of the data?

The expected size of data will be identified in the next version of this report (DMP), namely D8.I.3 Data Management Plan revision period 2 according to data collected in WP3 and D3.3 Report on data collection campaigns.

2.5 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

The data collected and generated by the project is useful for a wide range of stakeholders that are working in transport and gender related issues, including the following five main groups:

- Government / Authorities
- Business / Operators
- Associations / Advocates
- Scientific, academic and educational community
- Society in general

The following table provides details of the targeted users for each stakeholder group that will benefit from the data collected and generated by DIAMOND project.

Stakeholders' groups	Targeted users
Government / Authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elected officials at EU, national, regional and local level • Policy makers at EU, national, regional and local level • Transport planners and strategists • Public transport operators and transport organisers • HR managers, health and safety • Traffic police, emergency services
Businesses / operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public or private transport operators/ service providers • Vehicle manufacturers and their providers (Tier 1) • Car-sharing companies • Bicycle rental operators • New mobility services providers/start-ups • Transport consultants • Data specialists and technology consultants • Engineering and infrastructure design companies • Head-hunters, HR agencies • Insurance companies
Associations and advocates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport-related associations/advocates • Gender-related associations/advocates • Trade unions
Scientific, academic and educational community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions in transport, gender, sociology-related areas • Decision-makers and HR staff from universities, vocational / training centres • Research projects
Society in general	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communities (local interest groups, cycling/walking groups, public transport user groups, local authority forums) • Transport or gender-related NGOs • Media, bloggers • Individual citizens

Table 6. Detail of targeted users benefiting from DIAMOND project

3. FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Metadata provision

Data will be stored at a cloud-based repository (DIAMOND SharePoint repository) which is managed by EURECAT. Data will be kept for 2 years after the end of the project. Where requested, data will be kept for 2 more years, accessible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate, free of charge. Strong file-naming conventions and versioning applications will be of use to make data findable.

3.1.2 Standards for metadata creation

Data will only be shared out with the consortium in relation to publications (deliverables and papers). Considering publication will be the main piece of metadata for the shared data. The bibliographic metadata will be in a standard format and will include all the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

The full dataset is available to the members of the consortium. The following tables provide the complete list of DIAMOND project deliverables and their respective dissemination level as described in the grant agreement including both reports and Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP). The front page and executive summary will be published on the project website for all deliverables. There are no Deliverables considered as classified.

WP	Deliverable No	Title	Nature	Dissemination level
WP1	D1.1	Project administrative toolset	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP1	D1.2	Project quality plan	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP1	D1.3	Project Communication plan	Report	Public
WP2	D2.1	Use-cases definition	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP2	D2.2	Methodology and Conceptual framework	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

WP3	D3.1	Methodology and requirements for data collection	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP3	D3.2	User engagement strategy	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP3	D3.3	Report on data collection campaigns	Report	Public
WP4	D4.1	Datasets description	Other	Public
WP4	D4.2	Socio-economic, demographic and psychological analysis for women in transport related choices (transport modalities and jobs)	Report	Public
WP4	D4.3	Computational analysis report	Report	Public
WP4	D4.4	Integrated interdisciplinary analysis report	Report	Public
WP5	D5.1	Architecture design	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP5	D5.2	Toolbox source code	Other	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP6	D6.1	Report on the testing of the toolbox in the studied use-cases	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP6	D6.2	Evaluation and validation of fairness	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP7	D7.1	First Impact assessment report	Report	Public
WP7	D7.2	Interim Impact assessment report	Report	Public
WP7	D7.3	Final Impact assessment report	Report	Public
WP8	D8.1	Data Management Plan	ORDP	Public
WP8	D8.1.2	Data Management Plan revision period 1	ORDP	Public
WP8	D8.1.3	Data Management Plan revision period 2	ORDP	Public
WP8	D8.2	A Guide to interview ethics	Report	Public
WP8	D8.3	DIAMOND RRI and legal first year report	Report	Public
WP8	D8.4	DIAMOND RRI and legal second year report	Report	Public

WP8	D8.5	DIAMOND RRI and legal final report	Report	Public
WP9	D9.1	CSR protocols	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP9	D9.2	Educational curriculum design guidelines	Report	Public
WP9	D9.3	Guidelines on emotional needs in L4+ autonomous driving	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP9	D9.4	DIAMOND White Paper for a fair, inclusive and women-participated mobility and transport system	Report	Public
WP9	D9.5	First year dissemination and exploitation report	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP9	D9.6	Second year dissemination and exploitation report	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP9	D9.7	Final dissemination and exploitation report	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP9	D9.8	Innovation Management outcomes analysis	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
WP10	D10.1	NEC - Requirement No. 1	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Table 7. List of DIAMOND project deliverables and their dissemination level.

In addition, articles published in open access international scientific journals, workshops and academic conference abstracts/articles will be available for free access through the project website.

It is noteworthy that the data collected by IBV for observations for Use Case II, will be made available for re-use by archiving in the central institutional servers in IBV's facilities. Individuals will be duly informed through informed consent that IBV researchers will have access to pseudonymized data for IBV research and development projects. Data can be shared with other organizations after proper anonymization.

3.3 Making data interoperable

The concept interoperable demands that both data and metadata must be machine-readable and that a consistent terminology is used. The Data Managing team ensured also the increase of data re-use through open or non-proprietary formats and licences.

4. Data security

The DIAMOND project collected and processed specific data sets to develop the previously mentioned objectives, proposed studies and tools. Considering the possibility of collecting personal data, sensitive personal data and/or confidential private information for the purpose of the project, all processing will be conducted securely as per current General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) (EU, 2016/679). Transfer of data will be via a Zip process of distribution and Data Owner/Data Provider is responsible for the anonymization process and for ensuring that identifiable variables are not transferred to the repository.

4.1 Data Protection Officer

A data protection officer is responsible for overseeing an organization's data protection strategy and implementation. They are the officer that ensures that an organization is complying with the GDPR's requirements. According to GDPR Article 39, a data protection officer's responsibility includes¹¹:

- Training organization employees on GDPR compliance requirements
- Conducting regular assessments and audits to ensure GDPR compliance
- Serving as the point of contact between the company and the relevant supervisory authority
- Maintaining records of all data processing activities conducted by the company
- Responding to data subjects to inform them about how their personal data is being used and what measures the company has put in place to protect their data
- Ensuring that data subjects' requests to see copies of their personal data or to have their person data erased are fulfilled or responded to, as necessary.

The data protection officer for DIAMOND project is EURECAT.

5. Ethical issues

The consortium is aware that several privacy and data protection issues could be raised by the activities regarding surveys and interviews that require human participation and data collection from social media. These activities were done in full compliance with all European, national and institutional frameworks, legislation and directives relevant to the country and organisation where the data collections were taking place. Details of the guidelines used are provided in 'Deliverable 8.2 A Guide to interview ethics' as part of 'WP8 Ethical, legal and data management aspects' of DIAMOND project.

All data were anonymised, to protect any sensitive information about the users and in order not to have any potential ethical issues with their publication and dissemination, according to Article No. 8 and No. 13 of the GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation (EU, 2016/679). To ensure this, all participants were made fully aware that their involvement requires the submission of an

¹¹ <https://gdpr.eu/data-protection-officer-responsibilities/>

Informed Consent Form, prior to their participation. See Appendix I. to III. for detailed information.

EURECAT and the other relevant Diamond Partners collecting data are responsible for the anonymization process and for ensuring that identifiable variables are not transferred to the repository as per GDPR requirements. Directly identifiable variables include - but are not limited to - name, phone number, ZIP-code, e-mail address, home address, geographical coordinates (at a resolution that risks identification). The process is overseen by the Diamond Ethics committee.

5.1 Gender Analysis and Commitment to the Responsible Research Innovation (RRI) Principles

The DIAMOND Project acts in compliance and accordance with the best practices and principles of the RRI-Responsible Research and Innovation, in relation to the following aspects:

1. **Governance:** The governance of the Project addresses the responsibility of the Research Team in the design and execution of the research activities, with reference to prevent potential harmful or unethical developments.
2. **Public engagement:** DIAMOND's plan for public engagement includes the dissemination and communication activities, user engagement and their involvement in the co-design of the solution (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5) and its testing and validation (WP6). These plans also involve the Advisory Board and supporting organisations. Moreover, the application of the Dynamic Argumentative Delphi (DAD) method is used as a means for public engagement during and beyond the project frame. DIAMOND outputs will be made available open access. This includes training materials that will be used by educators in transport education initiatives. From these crosscutting activities, the project will distil in deliverables and in the Periodic Reports insights that may lead to improved RRI governance models and for the integration of its dimensions.
3. **Open access:** the materials, raw data and results of the Project are preferably published on peer-reviewed scientific research papers by using open access platforms, such as OpenAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe). This guarantees free online access to publications for the end-users (free of charge to read, download, copy, distribute and search content), accelerating dissemination and scientific progress.
4. **Gender equity and analysis:** All partners have in operation instances of measures for (i) ensuring equal opportunities in relation to HR processes (e.g. recruitment, training, promotion, work-life balance, etc.), (ii) addressing gender-related biases and under-representation; and, (iii) carrying out gender-sensitive research and innovation by promoting a balanced gender composition of the staff working on projects. As a result, even when men traditionally cover the areas of innovation related to DIAMOND, representatives of both genders will work under the supervision of the female DIAMOND Project Manager. Consistent with the above, DIAMOND carried out gender-sensitive analysis and design by acknowledging gender in every aspect of the analysis formulation, methodology, and outcome planning. The main addressable gender-related issues in the project are the consideration of Gender balanced end-user target groups for designing and validating the solution. Starting from the need for more inclusive transport systems, women are placed at the centre of the study, as users of transport and jobholders, and as transport planners, transport design and job hiring decision makers. However,

representatives of involved stakeholders, transport users and jobholders in the data collection, testing and validation activities of the DIAMOND solutions are selected considering the whole Gender, not only women, so as to avoid gender-based biases that may be created by only focusing on women's needs.

5. **Ethics:** The research is being carried out in accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki and of the Oviedo Convention and was evaluated by the Ethical Committee of the DIAMOND project. Moreover, concerning the protection and safety of the staff involved in this project, the partners involved in the project complied with the appropriate health and safety procedures in conformity to the relevant European and national legislation. The project data are treated in compliance with the relevant National Data Protection Authorities and with the EU General Data Protection Regulation. Informed consent from participants was requested after informing them about the goals of the project and the details of the questionnaires administered. See Appendix I. to III for detailed information. The consent was voluntarily and renegotiable, so that participants were able to withdraw at any stage of the research process. The project's privacy policy was also communicated to participants in order to inform them about what data will be collected, why it will be collected, who will be responsible for it and what the research team will do with it.
6. **Recruitment:** All recruitment procedures were carried out in full compliance with the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. Each member of the research team has vast experience in recruitment and was responsible for the proper announcement.

6. Appendix I. Participant Information Sheet

Invitation

You are being invited to consider taking part in the following research study.

DIAMOND Project Participant Information Sheet

DIAMOND - Revealing fair and actionable knowledge from data to support women's inclusion in Transport systems.

Purpose of the project:

DIAMOND is a research project to help identify and test how to make the current transport system fairer to all, and particularly for women. [or specify the part of the system as appropriate] It is funded by the European Union¹ and involves 14 partners from 10 EU countries including academics, transport operators and planners, public authorities and experts in infrastructure assessment design. The knowledge gathered in the data analysis will then be fed into a toolbox that will provide recommendations.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been invited to take part in your capacity as a member of a transport organisation/employer in the transport sector/employee in the transport sector/user of public transport.

What does participation involve?

1. You are being asked to take part in an interview and/or focus group which should last approximately 1.5 hours. You will be asked questions regarding the concept of fairness in transport use and employment for women, the barriers to fairness and requirements needed to improve fairness.
2. The interview will take place at a place and time convenient to yourself and your line manager.
3. You will also be asked to sign a permission form to allow the interview to be recorded. The recording will be used to make a more accurate transcription of the discussions taking place. The recordings will not be made available to anyone outside of the DIAMOND project and will be deleted within 6 months of the project finishing.
4. Findings from the interviews will be passed to project partners in an anonymous form. Individual transcripts will only be shared with project partners if a question arises about an entry in the aggregate table.
5. All information gathered will be treated as anonymous and confidential. No data will be revealed which could identify any respondent or group taking part in this project.
6. You are free to decide whether you wish to take part or not: your participation is entirely voluntary. Deciding not to take part in this project will carry no penalties. If you do decide to take part you will be asked to sign two Consent Forms, one is for you to keep and the other is for our records.
7. You can decline to answer any questions without giving a reason why.
8. If you change your mind during the study you are free to withdraw yourself and your data up until

9. All information gathered will be used to complete the project and any possible associated academic papers.

10. Potential commercial exploitation – the results of this interview may be used in the development of potential commercial products such as [***This part only applies where relevant, otherwise delete it.***]

11. Do you have any questions?

If you have any concerns about this study or if you are interested in obtaining the research results, please contact me at cc@ABC.com or tel. +44 xxx xxx.

7. Appendix II. Consent Form

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

DIAMOND - Revealing fair and actionable knowledge from data to support women's inclusion in Transport systems.

Please answer the following questions by ticking the response that applies

- | | YES | NO |
|--|-----|----|
| 1. I have read the information Sheet for this study and have had details of the study explained to me. | | |
| 2. Any questions I had about the study have been answered to my satisfaction and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point. | | |
| 3. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason for my withdrawal or to decline to answer any questions in the study without any consequences to my future treatment by the researcher. | | |
| 4. I agree to provide information to the researchers under the conditions of confidentiality set out in the information Sheet. | | |
| 5. I wish to participate in the study under the conditions set out in the information Sheet. | | |
| 6. I consent to an audio recording being made of this interview. | | |
| 7. I consent to the information collected for the purposes of this research study, once anonymised (so that I cannot be identified), to be used for any other research purposes related to the DIAMOND project (e.g. academic publications). | | |

Participant's Signature: _____ Date: _____

Participant's Name (Printed): _____

Contact details:

Researcher's Name (Printed)

Researcher's Signature: _____

8. Appendix III. Debrief Sheet

Debriefing Form for Participation in a Research Study XXX from XXX Organisation.

Thank you for your participation in our study!
Your participation is really appreciated.

Purpose of the Study:

We previously informed you that the purpose of the study was [insert brief sentence about purpose of study]. The goal of our research is to [insert statement(s) describing any research hypotheses and the results/findings you were/are looking for]. The next stage of this research is to analyse these results and attempt to create a picture of.....and any associated challenges.

I am of course happy to answer any additional questions you may have. I can do this just now or else my contact details are included in the information Sheet.

Confidentiality:

You may decide that you do not want your data used in this research. If you would like your data removed from the study and permanently deleted, please [insert instructions on how participant can have study data deleted].

Final Report:

If you would like to receive a copy of the final report of this study (or a summary of the findings) when it is completed, please feel free to contact us.

Useful Contact Information:

If you have any questions concerning your rights as a research subject, you may contact.....

Further Reading(s):

Provide two references (text, article, on-line reference, etc.) that can be easily accessed by the targeted population in this study.

